

Contextualized spatio-temporal graph-based method for forecasting sparse geospatial sensor networks

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ABSTRACT

Spatio-temporal forecasting is a rapidly evolving field, accelerated by the increasing accessibility of sensing infrastructure and computational hardware, capable of processing the large amount of sampled data. Applications of spatio-temporal forecasts range from traffic, weather, air pollution forecasting and others. Emerging technologies employ deep learning architectures, such as graph, convolutional, recurrent and transformer neural networks. While the state-of-the-art methods provide accurate time series predictions, they are typically limited to providing forecasts only for the direct locations of sampling, whereas coverage of the entire area is often desired by the applications. In this work, we propose a method that addresses this challenge and improves on the shortcomings of related works, which have already tackled the task. The proposed graph convolutional recurrent neural network based method provides forecasts for arbitrary geolocations without available measurement data, formulating predictions based on contextual information of target geolocations and the time series data of nearby measurement geolocations. We evaluate the method on three real-world datasets from meteorological, traffic and air pollution domains, and gauge its performance against the state-of-the-art spatio-temporal forecasting methods. The proposed method achieves 12.26%, 66.97% and 42.89% improvements in the mean absolute percentage errors on the three aforementioned datasets, compared to the best performing state-of-the-art method GConvGRU.

1. Introduction

Spatio-temporal data defines a collection of samples with spatial and temporal information. In practice, such data is often acquired by distributed sensor networks, where a set of variables is sampled on different locations. This form of sampling results in the (multivariate) time series, each associated with the location of the measurement.

With the decrease in costs of sensors and the supporting infrastructure for data collection and storage, and overall improvements in the field of internet of things (IoT), acquiring extensive spatio-temporal datasets of complex systems has become feasible, opening new possibilities for statistical methods to aid or replace otherwise manual tasks performed by the experts. Furthermore, the improved computational capabilities of the graphical processing units, have made possible for complex deep learning models and methods, to process the large amounts of high-dimensional data, that the distributed sensor networks produce (Wikle & Zammit-Mangion, 2023).

Modeling of spatio-temporal data allows for analysis of complex systems and events, improving on the expressiveness of the models which

operate on the time series information only (Tascikaraoglu, 2018). Successful applications of spatio-temporal forecasting include traffic forecasting (Luo et al., 2024; Yin et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2020), service demand forecasting (Geng et al., 2019; Guo & Zhang, 2020; Ke et al., 2017), weather forecasting (Castro et al., 2021; García-Duarte et al., 2023; Ma et al., 2023), air quality prediction (Abirami & Chitra, 2021; Hu et al., 2022; Yan et al., 2021), and photovoltaics (Karimi et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2021).

The existing approaches include graph convolutional recurrent neural networks (GCRNNs), which are based on modeling spatio-temporal measurement as a graph of time series (Cui et al., 2019; Seo et al., 2016), transformer architectures, which employ attention mechanism to assign varying degrees of importance to input samples (Luo et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2021), as well as different combinations of convolutional, graph, recurrent and transformer based neural networks (Castro et al., 2021; Qi et al., 2019). The research of aforementioned methods is particularly interesting, since the most successful methods are often applied with some modifications in various other fields too, such as healthcare, physiology and sport science

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(Ahmedt-Aristizabal et al., 2021; Bessadok et al., 2022; Yi et al., 2022), chemistry and biology (Alawad et al., 2024; Jha et al., 2022; Xia et al., 2021), and finance (Jeyaraman et al., 2024; Lazcano et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2023).

Although the existing methods provide good forecasting results, they are limited to making predictions only for locations with available time series data. While the measurements are collected in the manner of sparse locations, the results covering the entire area often tend to be more desirable in the real-world applications. Interpolative methods can be applied to fill the gaps between the locations of sampling, however, they do not account for the features of the interpolated area, and thus produce unsatisfactory results on the heterogeneous areas. For example; interpolated air quality between the measurement stations near high pollution sources will be low, even if the area is greatly covered by a forest, improving the air quality. Sparse sensing locations further exacerbate this problem, as the interpolation error increases with the distance from control points.

Among the spatio-temporal forecasting works, there are only a handful of approaches that focused on improving the spatial resolution of the forecasting. Le et. al. propose a method of spatio-temporal forecasting of air pollution (Le et al., 2020). The method is based on transforming the data into the series of gray-scale images by rasterizing the covered area, aggregating the measurements within the same pixel and leaving the pixels without measurement data blank. Convolutional long short-term memory (ConvLSTM) neural network (Shi et al., 2015) is used to interpret the sparse input images and produce forecast in the form of a dense grid. Similarly, Nag et al. (2023) propose the use of DeepKriging spatial interpolation method (Chen et al., 2020) to transform the input data from sparse points into the grid, and use ConvLSTM to procure forecasts. A major drawback of such approaches is the compromised quality of the input data to the ConvLSTM neural network training pipeline. Interpolation of data between the measurement locations introduces error, which greatly hinders ConvLSTM's ability to learn spatio-temporal features. Whereas the pixels near sampling locations hold relatively accurate values, larger gaps between the control points hold values which can greatly differ from the actual status. Finally, Najafi et al. (2022) propose a method for estimating the missing samples in a spatio-temporal data, which is based on temporal graph neural network. While the method is capable of procuring forecasts for locations with missing data, it is limited to only filling out the gaps in the time series for existing graph nodes, and not suitable for prediction for locations with no measurement data available.

To address these shortcomings, we propose a novel spatio-temporal forecasting method, which can produce time series forecasts for arbitrary geolocations without sensory data. The method significantly improves on the accuracy of the interpolative approaches, by incorporating contextual information of the geolocation of forecast, as well as the time series data of nearby geolocations. The contributions of this paper are the following:

- Extension of graph convolutional gated recurrent unit (GConvGRU) (Seo et al., 2016) by incorporating contextual information of measurement geolocations (such as terrain elevation, vegetation index etc.), as well as adoption of encoder-decoder structure, allowing for the use of known future variables.
- Modification of proposed forecasting model to additionally provide forecasts for geolocations without available time series data.
- Specific tailored training and evaluation algorithm for training the proposed architecture.
- The forecasting model is evaluated on three real-world datasets, performing tasks of numerical weather forecasting (NWP), traffic forecasting, and air pollutant forecasting. The proposed method is shown to outperform different methods utilizing interpolation at forecasting values for geolocations without measurement data.

The paper is structured as follows: Methodology section defines the forecasting task, describes the forecasting model architecture and presents the novel algorithm for forecasting sparse spatio-temporal data. Section Results provides details on experiments that were conducted to evaluate the performance of the proposed method. The Conclusion section reflects on the contributions and results of this work and proposes possible applications of the method and the future work.

2. Methodology

In the scope of the research, we address the spatio-temporal forecasting task, in which the time series data is being collected on different remote geolocations. The structure of the data can thus be described as a graph of time series, where the nodes of the graph denote the geolocations of sampling and the edges denote relations between the nodes. Each node is associated with a time series, a series of measurements of different variables, sampled on the corresponding geolocation. The task, which this work is addressing, is forecasting unknown future samples in time series of different nodes, based on past samples of each node, and their neighbourhood. We define the forecasting task using the rule (1).

$$(N \times W_{hist} \times F_{in}) \rightarrow (N \times W_{horizon} \times F_{out}) \quad (1)$$

where N denotes the number of nodes, W_{hist} denotes the length of the lookback history window in samples, $W_{horizon}$ denotes the length of the forecasting horizon in samples, F_{in} denotes the number of input time series variables, and finally F_{out} denotes the number of output time series variables that are being forecast.

2.1. Forecasting model architecture

Our forecasting model adopts the architectural designs of graph convolutional neural networks (GCNN) and recurrent neural networks (RNN). The role of graph convolutional structure in the network is to model the spatial relations between the nodes in graph—or, in our case—sensors distributed in space. On the other hand, the recurrent structure in the networks models the temporal relations between the samples in time series, associated with the nodes (sensors). Through preliminary empirical experimentation, we have found the best performing architecture, that implements the aforementioned structures, to be Graph Convolutional Gated Recurrent Unit (GConvGRU) (Seo et al., 2016), implementing Chebyshev graph convolution operator and a Gated Recurrent Unit.

More specifically, our forecasting model architecture is comprised of two such GConvGRUs. One, called encoder, is used to encode the past events in spatio-temporal data, that happened within the look-back history window of length W_{hist} . The input features of this unit are all available features F_{in} of the time series data. The other unit, called decoder, is used to decode the past events encoded by the encoder unit, by unrolling over the future timesteps. The inputs of the decoder unit are features known in advance (future), e.g. time of the day, day in year, scheduled road work, and similar.

Along with the time series data, nodes also possess the metadata, or explanatory variables, that provide the context of the node (node's features, surroundings, and local events). This presents a vital piece of information for forecasting, and can be further exploited to infer the forecast values even in cases, where the time series data is not available for the node at the time. To introduce this explanatory information to our forecasting model, we use the following pipeline:

1. Raster contextual information r of each node $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ (such as digital terrain model - DTM, for example) is extracted into a feature vector using three consecutive convolutional layers (CNN), denoted by Eq. (2). The kernel size used on each of the three CNN layers is 3×3 , number of filters 64, and the activation function applied to each layer's output is Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU). Since

Fig. 1. The complete architecture of the forecasting model.

all raster-based contextual information comes from the satellite imagery of equal resolution, multiple features are simply overlaid to form a multidimensional raster.

$$\mathbf{f}_i = f_{\text{CNN}}(\mathbf{r}_i) \quad (2)$$

- Other contextual features c are concatenated with the feature vector from previous step, formalized in Eq. (3).

$$\mathbf{z}_i = [\mathbf{f}_i; \mathbf{c}_i] \quad (3)$$

- A dense (linear) layer is used to transform the feature vector into a M -dimensional vector. The vector encapsulates a high-dimensional representation of node's contextual information, and is shown in Eq. (4). The process in steps 1–3 is performed on each node in the graph, forming a graph of nodes with M features.

$$\mathbf{v}_i = f_{\text{Linear}}(\mathbf{z}_i) \quad (4)$$

- The extracted contextual information v_i of each node is shared within the graph using a graph convolution layer with Chebyshev filter, as demonstrated by the Eq. (5).

$$\mathbf{v}'_i = f_{\text{GCN}}(\mathbf{v}_i) \quad (5)$$

- The result is used to initialize the hidden state of the encoder GConvGRU, providing the unit with the contextual information of individual nodes and their neighbors, which is finally shown in Eq. (11).

$$\mathbf{h}_i^{\text{encoder}} = \mathbf{v}'_i \quad (6)$$

The pipeline for processing contextual features is graphically depicted in Fig. 1, in a dashed box marked with letter A. The numbers on the figure enumerate the steps in the pipeline.

2.2. Algorithm for forecasting spatially sparse data

To improve the spatial resolution of the forecasts, we propose a method for generating forecasts for geolocations without available sensory data, based on contextual information of the geolocation and

spatio-temporal data of the neighboring geolocations. To that end, the forecasting model and the training strategy are adapted for the task.

Thus far, both the forecasting task's input and output, were the same graphs of time series, as denoted by the parameter N in rule (1). With the introduction of additional geolocations, where the forecast is needed, the output graph is extended with additional nodes, while the input graph remains the same (as the time series for new geolocations are not available). The change in the forecasting task is evidenced in rule (7).

$$[N \times W_{\text{hist}} \times F_{\text{in}}] \rightarrow [(N + N_{\text{new}}) \times W_{\text{horizon}} \times F_{\text{out}}] \quad (7)$$

For the model to accommodate this change, we modify the way encoder's spatio-temporal information is passed into the decoder. While the encoder still encodes the spatio-temporal data of a graph with N nodes, the decoder now unrolls this information over time for the new graph with $N + N_{\text{new}}$ nodes. To provide the decoder with spatio-temporal context of past events and the contextual information of new nodes, the following method is applied to enrich the $[N \times M]$ dimensional encoding into a $[(N + N_{\text{new}}) \times M]$ one:

- M -dimensional representations v_j of contextual information of all nodes $J \in \{1, 2, \dots, N + N_{\text{new}}\}$, including new ones, are acquired following the steps 1–3 from Section 2.1.
- The contextual information v_j is concatenated with the spatio-temporal encoding $\mathbf{h}_i^{\text{encoder}}$ of the encoder GConvGRU. For the N_{new} nodes with no corresponding spatio-temporal encoding, zeros are used. The step is formalized in the Eq. (8).

$$\mathbf{st}_J = \begin{cases} [\mathbf{h}_i^{\text{encoder}}; \mathbf{v}_i], & \text{for } i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}, \\ [\mathbf{0}; \mathbf{v}_j], & \text{for } j \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_{\text{new}}\}. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

- A dense (linear) layer is used to perform a dimensionality reduction of nodes spatio-temporal and contextual encodings \mathbf{st}_J from $2 * M$, back to M features per node, as shown by Eq. (9).

$$\mathbf{v}_J = f_{\text{Linear}}(\mathbf{st}_J) \quad (9)$$

Algorithm 1 Initialization of input variables and neural network layers.

```

/* Initialize input variables */
 $r_i \leftarrow$  contextual raster data for real nodes,  $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 7 \times 7 \times F_r}$ 
 $r_j \leftarrow$  contextual raster data for virtual nodes,  $r_j \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{new} \times 7 \times 7 \times F_r}$ 
 $c_i \leftarrow$  other contextual data for real nodes,  $c_i \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times F_{other}}$ 
 $c_j \leftarrow$  other contextual data for virtual nodes,  $c_j \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{new} \times F_{other}}$ 
 $G_i \leftarrow$  edges between real nodes,  $G_i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}^2$ 
 $G_J \leftarrow$  edges between all nodes,  $G_J \in \{1, 2, \dots, N + N_{new}\}^2$ 
 $x_{i,T}^{hist} \leftarrow$  historical measurement time series data on real nodes,
 $x_{i,T}^{hist} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times W_{hist} \times (F_{in} + F_{known})}$ 
 $x_{j,T}^{horizon} \leftarrow$  known future time series data on all nodes,
 $x_{j,T}^{horizon} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N + N_{new}) \times W_{horizon} \times F_{known}}$ 
/* Initialize neural network architecture */
 $CNN_{filters} \leftarrow 64$ 
 $CNN_{kernel} \leftarrow 3$ 
 $M \leftarrow 64$ 
 $GCN_{filters} \leftarrow M$ 
 $K_{Cheb} \leftarrow 3$ 
 $CNN_1 \leftarrow$  Conv2D(in_channels =  $|F_{raster}|$ , out_channels =
 $CNN_{filters}$ , kernel_size =  $CNN_{kernel}$ )
 $CNN_2 \leftarrow$  Conv2D(in_channels =  $CNN_{filters}$ , out_channels =
 $CNN_{filters}$ , kernel_size =  $CNN_{kernel}$ )
 $CNN_3 \leftarrow$  Conv2D(in_channels =  $CNN_{filters}$ , out_channels =
 $CNN_{filters}$ , kernel_size =  $CNN_{kernel}$ )
 $Linear_s \leftarrow$  Linear(in_features =  $CNN_{filters} +$ 
 $|F_{other}|$ , out_features =  $GCN_{filters}$ )
 $Linear_{st} \leftarrow$  Linear(in_features =  $CNN_{filters} + |F_{other}|$ 
 $+ GCN_{filters}$ , out_features =  $GCN_{filters}$ )
 $Linear_t \leftarrow$  Linear(in_features =  $GCN_{filters}$ , out_features =  $|F_{out}|$ )
 $GCN_s \leftarrow$  ChebConv(in_channels =  $GCN_{filters}$ , out_channels =
 $GCN_{filters}$ ,  $K = K_{Cheb}$ )
 $GCN_{st} \leftarrow$  ChebConv(in_channels =  $GCN_{filters}$ , out_channels =
 $GCN_{filters}$ ,  $K = K_{Cheb}$ )
 $GCRN_{encoder} \leftarrow$  GConvGRU(in_channels =  $|F_{in}|$ 
 $+ |F_{known}|$ , out_channels =  $GCN_{filters}$ ,  $K = K_{Cheb}$ )
 $GCRN_{decoder} \leftarrow$  GConvGRU(in_channels =  $|F_{known}|$ ,
out_channels =  $GCN_{filters}$ ,  $K = K_{Cheb}$ )

```

4. The graph convolutional layer is used to propagate the combination of spatio-temporal and contextual information to neighboring nodes in the graph, denoted in Eq. (10).

$$v'_j = f_{GCN}(v_j) \quad (10)$$

5. The result is used to initialize the hidden state of the decoder, as defined by the Eq. (11).

$$h_J^{decoder} = v'_j \quad (11)$$

The algorithm is visually presented in Fig. 1, in a dashed box marked with letter B. The steps in the algorithm are denoted with numbers next to fixtures in the schematic.

The complete architecture of the forecasting model is presented in Fig. 1. The inputs of the forecasting model are colored in green and consist of the node contextual features and the time series obtained from the corresponding measurement geolocations. Examples of input and output graphs of time series are provided to demonstrate how the method generates predictions for arbitrary geolocations. The example of the graph on the top of the schematic denotes the input graph of time series, consisting only of N nodes, which correspond to measurement geolocations with collected time series data, colored in blue. The graph on the bottom extends the aforementioned graph with N_{new} virtual nodes without available time series data, colored in magenta. Same color scheme (blue

Algorithm 2 Definition of the proposed neural network architecture forward pass algorithm.

```

procedure CNN_FORWARD( $r$ )
 $c \leftarrow CNN_1(r)$ 
 $c \leftarrow \text{ReLU}(c)$ 
 $c \leftarrow CNN_2(c)$ 
 $c \leftarrow \text{ReLU}(c)$ 
 $c \leftarrow CNN_3(c)$ 
 $c \leftarrow \text{ReLU}(c)$ 
 $c_i \leftarrow \text{SoftMax}(c, \text{dim} = 1)$ 
procedure FORWARD( $r_i, r_j, c_i, c_j, x_{i,T}^{hist}, x_{j,T}^{horizon}, G_i, G_J$ )
 $f_i \leftarrow \text{CNN\_forward}(r_i)$ 
 $z_i \leftarrow [f_i; c_i]$ 
 $v_i \leftarrow \text{Linear}_s(z_i)$ 
 $v'_i \leftarrow GCN_s(v_i, G_i)$ 
 $h_i^{encoder} \leftarrow v'_i$ 
for  $t = 1$  to  $W_{hist}$  do
 $h_i^{encoder} \leftarrow GCRN_{encoder}(X = x_{i,T}^{hist}, \text{edge\_index} = G_i,$ 
 $H = h_i^{encoder})$ 
 $f_j \leftarrow \text{CNN\_forward}(r_j)$ 
 $z_j \leftarrow [f_j; c_j]$ 
 $v_j \leftarrow \text{Linear}_s(z_j)$ 
 $st_J \leftarrow \begin{cases} [h_i^{encoder}; v_i], & \text{for } i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}, \\ [0; v_j], & \text{for } j \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_{new}\}. \end{cases}$ 
 $v_J \leftarrow \text{Linear}_{st}(st_J)$ 
 $v'_J \leftarrow GCN_{st}(v_J, G_J)$ 
 $h_J^{decoder} \leftarrow v'_J$ 
 $y \leftarrow []$ 
for  $t = 1$  to  $W_{horizon}$  do
 $h_J^{decoder} \leftarrow GCRN_{decoder}(X = x_{j,T}^{horizon}, \text{edge\_index} = G_J,$ 
 $H = h_J^{decoder})$ 
 $h \leftarrow \text{ReLU}(h_J^{decoder})$ 
 $y_{hat} \leftarrow \text{Linear}_t(h)$ 
 $y \leftarrow [y; y_{hat}]$ 
return  $y$ 

```

for real and magenta for virtual nodes) is applied to the labels of inputs, outputs and intermediate results of the model.

The initialization of the input variables and the neural network layers are presented in the pseudocode 1, and the forward pass algorithm of the proposed architecture is presented in pseudocode 2.

Training the model to predict on additional nodes without available time series requires the modification of the training strategy. The proposed strategy introduces the masking of nodes from the original graph, serving as targets to train the model for predictions on geolocations without the available time series data. More specifically, on each batch, $N_{virtual}$ nodes are selected at random, tasking the model to make predictions for the underlying geolocations without the time series data of those nodes. The number of masked nodes $N_{virtual}$ is selected as a ratio of all nodes in graph. The ratio of 20% ($N_{virtual} = [0.2 * N]$) was found to optimize the training performance and forecasting accuracy. The forecasting task during training can thus be described the following way: (12).

$$[(N - N_{virtual}) \times W_{hist} \times F_{in}] \rightarrow [N \times W_{horizon} \times F_{out}] \quad (12)$$

3. Results

In the following section, experiments conducted to develop and evaluate the proposed method are explained in detail. To provide the context of the experiments, we first describe the datasets used in the experiments

Table 1
Datasets used in this work.

Dataset	Sampling frequency	N	F_{in}	Known variables	Explanatory variables	F_{out}	Period	Graph structure
Meteorological	60 min	79	Temperature [°C] Relative humidity [%] Precipitation [mm] Wind speed [$\frac{m}{s}$] Wind direction [°]	Time of the day Day of the year	DTM NDVI Land use-classification	Temperature [°C] Relative humidity [%]	2018–2021	Weighted sum of distance and Δ elevation
Traffic	60 min	190	Slow vehicle count ^a Fast vehicle count ^b Average velocity [$\frac{km}{h}$] Temperature [°C] Precipitation [mm] Wind speed [$\frac{m}{s}$]	Time of the day Day of the week Day of the year T forecast [°C] Precip. fcast [mm] Traffic events-information Holiday information	Speed limit [$\frac{km}{h}$] Number of lanes Inclination [°]	Slow vehicle count Fast vehicle count Average velocity [$\frac{km}{h}$]	2018–2021 ^c	Road length Road network topology
Air pollutant	60 min	8	NO ₂ [$\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$] O ₃ [$\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$] PM10 [$\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$] Temperature [°C] Relative humidity [%] Precipitation [mm] Wind speed [$\frac{m}{s}$] Wind direction [°]	Time of the day Day of the week Day of the year T forecast [°C] Precip. fcast [mm]	DTM NDVI Land use-classification	NO ₂ [$\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$] O ₃ [$\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$] PM10 [$\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	2018–2021	Distance

^a Vehicles of categories A to B1.

^b Vehicles of categories B2 and heavier.

^c The period during initial COVID pandemic in Slovenia is exempted.

and the evaluation metrics and benchmark methods. Then, we briefly describe the parametrization of the forecasting model that is described in Section 2.1. Finally, we provide the details of the experiments that we conducted to evaluate the proposed method for forecasting spatially sparse data, which is described in the Section 2.2.

3.1. Datasets

The methods developed in this work are evaluated on three different spatio-temporal datasets. The datasets include: 1) weather dataset of numerical weather parameters measured by meteorological stations across Slovenia, 2) traffic dataset of vehicle counters and velocities measured by the radar infrastructure of Slovenian highway agency, and 3) air pollutant dataset of Slovenian agency of environment. The dataset information is summarized in Table 1. Examples of yearly and weekly profiles for the three datasets are provided in Fig. 2.

3.2. Metrics and benchmark methods

The forecast methods used in this work are evaluated using metrics root mean squared error (RMSE), and min-max normalized percentage MAE. The metrics are formalized in Eq. (13), where symbols x_f and x_g denote forecasted and ground truth sample values and x_{\max} and x_{\min} denote largest and smallest sample values in the dataset.

$$\begin{aligned}
 RMSE &= \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_f - x_g)^2} \\
 MAE &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_f - x_g| \\
 MAPE &= \frac{MAE}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}} \times 100
 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

The naive benchmarks used in this work are based on the last observation, an observations 24 h ago, and 7 days ago. We define them in the

following rule: (14).

$$\begin{aligned}
 NAIVE_f : x_t &:= x_{t-1} \\
 NAIVE_d : x_t &:= x_{t-d}, d = 24 \\
 NAIVE_w : x_t &:= x_{t-w}, w = 7 \times 24
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

where w_t denotes the predicted sample at timestep t .

The models are always evaluated based on their forecast of multiple samples in the future. The selected forecasting horizon is 6 h, which translates into $W_{horizon} = 6$ forecasted samples.

3.3. Parametrization of the forecasting model

To find the optimal forecasting model for the prediction task defined in (1), the standard procedure of grid search sensitivity analysis for the model parametrization was conducted. Following are the parameters of the forecasting model, that were found to produce the best results:

- A single layer of GConvGRU was found to perform better than stacking 2 or more layers.
- The number of output features (dimensionality of the spatio-temporal encoding) of the GConvGRU cell that yielded best results was $M = 64$.
- The best Chebyshev filter size of graph convolution operator in GConvGRU cell was found to be 3.

Additionally, we used the length of the lookback history window $W_{hist} = 96$, batch size $B = 32$, learning rate of the Adam optimizer 0.005, trained the models for 3000 epochs and split the dataset between training, validation and test subsets in 2:1:1 ratio.

The results of the forecasting model in comparison with different benchmarks are presented in Table 2. The benchmarks used in the study perform well on the data, since it demonstrates strong periodic behaviour. Especially accurate are the samples from previous week for traffic forecasting, as the number of vehicles heavily depends on

Fig. 2. Examples of yearly and weekly profiles of meteorological, traffic and air pollutant datasets. The data was taken from one of the geolocations from each dataset.

the day of the week. Despite that, there are patterns in the data, that spatio-temporal forecasting architectures can learn from, to further improve on the accuracy achieved by the simple benchmarks, such as unusual events and explanatory variables, which can help predict target variables.

The results ablation study comparing different parametrizations of Chebyshev filter are presented in Table 3. A size of the filter equates to the number of hops on the graph. We found that lower sizes tend to perform better, especially on smaller graphs (such as in case of air pollutant dataset, where the smallest possible filter performs best). On the meteorological and traffic dataset, the size $K = 3$ performed best, which was the parametrization choice that we used in all further experiments.

3.4. Evaluation of the algorithm for spatially sparse data forecasting

The evaluation of the algorithm is conducted using the K-fold validation approach. The model is trained and evaluated K-times. Each run, a different subset of $\frac{1}{K} * N$ nodes is removed from the graph that the model is training on. When the training process is finished, the model is then tasked with performing the forecasts on the geolocations of removed nodes. The forecasts in removed nodes are then evaluated against the actual measurements. The results of K runs on each dataset is summarized in Table 4.

The accuracy of the proposed algorithm is compared to the accuracy of different approaches utilizing interpolative methods. The first approach uses state-of-the-art GConvGRU neural network to predict future values for nodes with available time series data, which is followed by the 2D interpolation of forecasted samples. The second approach is the similar, but uses A3T-GCN (Attention Temporal Graph Convolutional Network) (Bai et al., 2021) for the predictive task. The third approach first performs the 2D interpolation that transforms the graph time series data into a sequence of rasters, which are then fed into the ConvLSTM neural network tasked to predict future frames. All approaches are evaluated in conjunction with two 2D interpolation methods; thin plate spline (TPS) interpolation (Duchon, 1977) and inverse distance weighting (IDW). The implementation of IDW follows the Eq. (15), where the w_i denotes the weight of the edge between the target node and neighbour i . On the traffic dataset, the TPS interpolation and the ConvLSTM-based approach were not applied, as the road network data can not be reasonably interpolated to fill the entire 2D grid.

$$x_{interp} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{neighbours} w_i * x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{neighbours} w_i} \quad (15)$$

The results achieved by the proposed method significantly outperform the compared state-of-the-art approaches. Especially on the traffic dataset, the results of benchmark methods are nearly

Table 2
Forecasting accuracy achieved by the forecasting model.

Dataset	Method	RMSE	MAPE
Meteorological	$NAIVE_f$	[5.102 °C, 19.93 %]	[7.514 %, 14.43 %]
	$NAIVE_d$	[3.400 °C, 16.32 %]	[4.989 %, 11.23 %]
	GConvGRU	[1.794 °C, 9.809 %]	[2.894 %, 6.574 %]
Traffic	$NAIVE_f$	[91.91, 357.0, 10.71 $\frac{km}{h}$]	[14.65 %, 9.857 %, 5.785 %]
	$NAIVE_d$	[71.21, 307.1, 9.548 $\frac{km}{h}$]	[10.92 %, 8.312 %, 4.845 %]
	$NAIVE_w$	[51.16, 287.3, 11.01 $\frac{km}{h}$]	[7.241 %, 7.825 %, 4.746 %]
	GConvGRU	[37.37, 213.6, 8.276 $\frac{km}{h}$]	[5.514 %, 5.547 %, 3.729 %]
Air pollutant	$NAIVE_f$	[14.70 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 25.57 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 19.79 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[8.885 %, 9.984 %, 6.878 %]
	$NAIVE_d$	[12.84 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 22.14 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 16.26 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[7.606 %, 8.338 %, 5.385 %]
	GConvGRU	[9.551 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 17.35 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 11.85 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[6.192 %, 8.083 %, 3.991 %]

Table 3
Forecasting accuracy achieved by the forecasting model using different Chebyshev filter sizes.

Dataset	Chebyshev filter size	RMSE	MAPE
Meteorological	1	[1.846 °C, 9.955 %]	[2.961 %, 6.661 %]
	2	[1.820 °C, 9.902 %]	[2.965 %, 6.708 %]
	3	[1.794 °C, 9.809 %]	[2.894 %, 6.574 %]
	4	[1.851 °C, 9.954 %]	[3.049 %, 6.759 %]
	10	[3.337 °C, 14.36 %]	[5.729 %, 10.11 %]
Traffic	1	[43.64, 271.8, 11.23 $\frac{km}{h}$]	[6.676 %, 7.566 %, 4.766 %]
	2	[41.25, 252.3, 11.11 $\frac{km}{h}$]	[6.266 %, 7.016 %, 4.621 %]
	3	[37.37, 213.6, 8.276 $\frac{km}{h}$]	[5.514 %, 5.547 %, 3.729 %]
	4	[44.10, 254.6, 12.38 $\frac{km}{h}$]	[6.643 %, 7.076 %, 4.981 %]
	10	[64.09, 438.3, 17.34 $\frac{km}{h}$]	[10.84 %, 13.36 %, 9.015 %]
Air pollutant	1	[9.377 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 17.25 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 11.79 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[6.155 %, 7.968 %, 3.960 %]
	2	[9.409 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 17.07 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 11.69 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[6.088 %, 7.825 %, 3.898 %]
	3	[9.551 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 17.35 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 11.85 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[6.192 %, 8.083 %, 3.991 %]
	4	[9.545 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 18.93 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 11.87 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[6.468 %, 8.765 %, 4.046 %]
	10	[10.53 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 25.01 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 13.14 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[7.216 %, 11.50 %, 4.471 %]

Table 4
Forecasting accuracy achieved by the proposed method on the unknown (masked) nodes.

Dataset, K	Method	RMSE	MAPE
Meteorological, K = 9	GConvGRU + TPS	[4.705 °C, 18.12 %]	[8.192 %, 13.14 %]
	GConvGRU + IDW	[4.972 °C, 19.51 %]	[8.770 %, 13.94 %]
	A3T-GCN + TPS	[5.148 °C, 19.04 %]	[8.889 %, 13.31 %]
	A3T-GCN + IDW	[5.202 °C, 19.76 %]	[8.940 %, 13.94 %]
	TPS + ConvLSTM	[8.176 °C, 19.22 %]	[13.40 %, 16.09 %]
	IDW + ConvLSTM	[8.001 °C, 19.19 %]	[13.13 %, 16.15 %]
	Proposed	[3.988 °C, 16.61 %]	[6.626 %, 12.43 %]
Traffic, K = 10	GConvGRU + IDW	[106.2, 792.9, 37.20 $\frac{km}{h}$]	[33.45 %, 44.90 %, 28.97 %]
	A3T-GCN + IDW	[126.0, 826.2, 39.71 $\frac{km}{h}$]	[37.92 %, 44.02 %, 29.93 %]
	Proposed	[92.11, 475.0, 24.03 $\frac{km}{h}$]	[10.60 %, 13.77 %, 10.64 %]
Air pollutant, K = 8	GConvGRU + TPS	[22.77 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 83.12 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 23.52 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[12.33 %, 31.11 %, 6.014 %]
	GConvGRU + IDW	[23.17 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 81.87 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 24.69 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[12.72 %, 30.93 %, 6.332 %]
	A3T-GCN + TPS	[22.84 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 79.31 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 22.87 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[11.92 %, 28.50 %, 6.237 %]
	A3T-GCN + IDW	[22.81 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 78.62 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 22.94 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[11.83 %, 28.39 %, 6.236 %]
	TPS + ConvLSTM	[26.30 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 92.02 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 27.62 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[13.95 %, 33.87 %, 6.764 %]
	IDW + ConvLSTM	[26.26 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 91.20 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 28.34 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[13.90 %, 32.93 %, 6.882 %]
	Proposed	[12.64 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 28.30 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$, 15.42 $\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$]	[7.236 %, 9.157 %, 5.005 %]

unusable, due to high error induced by the interpolative pre- or post-processing. The interpolation struggles to correctly model the heterogeneity of the area between the nodes, leading to errors in the post-processed results or invalid input training dataset samples if used in pre-processing.

The results achieved on the meteorological dataset for temperature feature are further explored in the following Figs. 3 and 4.

In Fig. 3, the forecasting error of different approaches is modelled w.r.t. the average distance to neighbouring nodes. Blue, red, green and magenta markers denote errors on stations of the proposed method, TPS interpolation preprocessing with ConvLSTM, GConvGRU, and A3T-GCN (Bai et al., 2021) with TPS postprocessing, respectively. The markers are highlighted if the method achieved the best result on the specific node (47 for proposed method, 21 for the GConvGRU, 8 for A3T-GCN and 3 out of 79 for the ConvLSTM).

Blue, red, green and magenta lines in Fig. 3 demonstrate the linear function estimates of the forecasting error w.r.t the distance to

control points, each modelling the corresponding forecasting method. The upward trend denotes the increase in forecasting error as the distance from control points increases. The proposed method (blue) demonstrates both the lowest average error, as well as the most gradual (least steep) slope.

The results are visualized for geospatial positioning of meteorological sensors over Slovenia in Fig. 4. The background of the image resembles the digital terrain model of the observed geographical area. The nodes are drawn on the geolocations of the meteorological stations and lines between them denote the edges of the graph. The nodes' colors denote the difference in the forecasting error between the proposed method and the next best performing method (GConvGRU). Green markers resemble nodes, where the proposed method performed better than the benchmark comparison, and red markers resemble nodes, where the proposed method performed worse. The size of the markers and the labels underneath them demonstrate the MAPE forecasting improvement in %.

Fig. 3. Comparison of the proposed approach with SOTA spatio-temporal methods when forecasting for nodes without available time series.

Fig. 4. Improvements of forecasting MAPE [%] achieved by the proposed method, compared to the result of the second best performing SOTA spatio-temporal forecasting method (GConvGRU) on each node.

4. Conclusion

The paper introduces a novel method of spatio-temporal forecasting for geolocations without available measurement data. Proposed method improves on the existing solutions, which are based on transforming the data into the grid format, or postprocessing the results, by working with the graph structured data. We evaluated the method on three real-world datasets, comparing the performance of the spatio-temporal forecast with the state-of-the-art forecasting approaches used in conjunction with IDW and TPS interpolation methods. The proposed approach of spatio-temporal forecast outperforms said benchmark methods on all datasets. Furthermore, the proposed approach outperforms the best out of any selected benchmark method on 47 out of 79 measurement geolocations on the meteorological dataset. The analysis of the results suggests that while the error of benchmark methods incorporating interpolation increases with the distance from control points, the proposed method retains robust forecasting performance even on longer distances. In the future work, the method could be applied together with the optimization algorithm for placement of virtual nodes for predictions. We speculate, that the most suitable use for the method is to create a dense network of crucial geolocations as virtual nodes (such as mountain ridges and valleys or road intersections), and only then fill out the empty spaces using interpolative approach.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Niko Uremović: Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft; **Domen Mongus:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Resources, Writing – review & editing; **Aleksander Pur:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing; **Niko Lukač:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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